

BuddyWall: A Tangible User Interface for Wireless Remote Communication

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Abstract

BuddyWall is a system comprised of a wall-mounted panel with mobile wireless objects that represent remote friends on a network. The purpose of this interface is to allow for communication among remotely located friends and to display an awareness of group presence and others' availability through an ambient wall display. This project illustrates the transparency of a physical interface that provides aesthetically pleasing and emotionally engaging access to digital information for anyone. This paper describes the design of the system and interaction techniques developed in the context of this work. The aesthetics of physical objects can also enrich the digital experience and make it emotionally evocative.

Conference theme: Teaching across cultures design

Keywords: Tangible interface, interaction design, networked objects, ubiquitous computing, ambient displays, augmented environments, emotional design.

Motivation and research background

Nowadays travel is relatively easy and much cheaper than in the past. This increasing mobility of humans has caused loved ones to spend most of their time apart from each other. Fortunately technology is now serving as a means for connecting people that are distant and making them aware of each other's presence at any time. In the past, people who separated physically would often separate socially and emotionally as well. Distance used to matter. Today the isolation once imposed by distance is no longer true. The current technology makes it possible to stay in touch with friends and family to an amount undreamed of earlier. The ability to exchange short text messages so effortlessly has become a strong emotional component of many people's lives. The real power of instant messaging is not the message itself (though that is a key attribute), but the presence detection it provides. It is a way of knowing that there are other people "with you", even if virtually.

The current communication technologies are allowing people to interact and stay emotionally connected. However, those interactions are currently limited to input via mouse and keyboard and output in the form of text, graphics and sound. Interactions confined to the traditional Graphical User Interfaces (GUI) are very distant from the ones that exist in the physical environment we live in. What if communication capabilities and presence detection could become integrated into people's natural environment? What if one could come home and see which friends are there and which ones are not without having to turn on a computer? The idea is to integrate this awareness into the environment.

For centuries humans have interacted with the real world through rich communications and haptic interactions with physical objects. Physical objects provide "tangibility" through its weight, texture and surface. With the rapid growth of digital technologies, much of this richness has been lost. Digital creations have moved from real physical controls and products to applications that reside inside a single "box" where information is manipulated on a computer screen by interactions involving only a mouse and keyboard. The notion of "tangibility", the sense of control and the pleasure of manipulating a physical object are then totally gone. Virtual worlds eliminate one of the greatest delights of real interactions: the delight that comes from touching, feeling and moving real physical objects. The current paradigm of Human Computer Interaction (HCI) with GUI and computer screens employs only a small fraction of a human's capability to communicate and interact. Physical objects involve the world of emotion, where one experiences things, and too much adherence to the abstraction of the computer screen subtracts from emotional pleasure. (Norman, 2004).

In 1991, Mark Weiser from Xerox PARC published an article on his vision of Ubiquitous Computing (Weiser, 1991) where he illustrates a different paradigm in HCI, which pushes computers into the background and attempts to make them invisible. The BuddyWall project adopts this emerging paradigm of thinking about computers: one that takes into account the human world and allows the computers themselves to vanish into the background. When the computer is moved to the background it will mean that users will use it without thinking and will be able to focus beyond them on new goals. Since ubiquitous computers reside in the human space, it poses no barrier to personal interactions. It could, in fact, bring communities closer together. We are moving towards machines that fit the human environment instead of forcing humans to enter theirs.

BuddyWall is based on the concept of Tangible User Interfaces (TUI) introduced by Hiroshi Ishii from the MIT Media Lab (Ishii and Ullmer, 1997). In transitioning from the GUI of desktop PCs to Tangible User Interfaces the world itself becomes an interface. Besides making use of a TUI for the manipulation of digital information without the use of a visible computer this project also engages both the center and the periphery of our attention, moving back and forth between the two. This form of “ambient media” can be seen as a window of awareness, which connects the person inside to the outside world (Weiser and Brown, 1995). The constant changing of the objects’ color and gentle incoming sounds moves easily to the background. By using ambient media as an additional source to convey information, this project takes advantage of our brain’s natural abilities as both a parallel processor and as an attention manager. Together with the concept of tangible digital information, the interface of this system has been constructed in a way that is intuitive, natural and compatible with our emotional status. Combining emotions and technology was an important part of the design process.

The aim of this project is to show one of the possible alternatives for moving beyond the current dominant model of the GUI and its limited interaction possibilities. The Ubiquitous Computing approach suggests that the real physical world be augmented by the coupling of digital information to everyday physical objects and environments. This project explores ways in which computing can be taken off the desk and integrated into everyday objects. BuddyWall aims to provide a physical connection between individuals. Through the use of ambient media, it brings a subtle and poetic representation of the presence of others by showing through light and sounds other people’s availability at any instant in time.

Related work

Previous work on ambient devices has concentrated on unobtrusively presenting information and making it available at a glance (Ambient Devices, 2001). Other ambient communication devices served as a way for remote presence detection (Deschamps-Sonsino, 2007). ComTouch (Chang, 2002) and LumiTouch (Chang, 2001) are examples of tangible devices that focus on non-verbal communication of emotional content as well as remote presence detection.

BuddyWall serves not only as an ambient display (Weiser and Brown, 1995) for providing presence detection and communicating emotional content but can also engage users in an active voice communication. It navigates in the attention requirement spectrum from ambient display to direct communication device (Chang, 2001).

ComSlipper (Chen et al., 2006) is an example of a communication device that uses an everyday object as a means for affective communication. When users engage in an emotionally rich communication by means of an interactive object they are predisposed to anthropomorphize, to project human emotions and beliefs into the device (Norman, 2004). Nabaztag (Haladjian and Mével, 2006) is similar to BuddyWall in the sense that it presents a device that is more emotionally engaging than an everyday object and can thus provide a closer connection with the user.

In light of the precedents reviewed, the BuddyWall proposes a Tangible User Interface that connects physical objects to the manipulation of digital information. It adds the display of ambient information about others' presence and allows for an emotional connection among remotely located friends.

Preliminary project: Amebeats

Unlike a GUI, which is well constrained by a program, the manipulation of objects in the physical world is much less constrained. When designing the interface and behaviors for this project it was necessary to identify, besides the interface, a fundamental set of interactions that were both appropriate to the task and also compatible with the current available technology.

The current design was inspired by the development and observations of user interactions with the Amebeats project (Quintanilha, 2006), a Tangible User Interface for the creation of music (figure 1). The goal with this project was to observe how people responded to the interface and interactions with a wall-mounted emotionally engaging tangible interface.

Figure 1: Amebeats, a Tangible User Interface that allows people to mix sounds by manipulating physical objects instead of twisting knobs or clicking buttons on music production software.

The Amebeats concept started with a rectangular design and evolved to an illuminated amoeba-shaped design. Users responded positively to the design and scale of this interface stating that it was an incentive to engage with the device. Users appreciated its ease of use and tactile interaction qualities. Objects were easily graspable and it was possible for more than one person to interact with it at the same time. Users also responded positively to the use of sound as an indication of change and the device's kinesthetic and tactile qualities that were different from the habitual interactions with computer software. All evidence from observations with this preliminary project served as guided intelligence in the design process of the BuddyWall.

System design

The BuddyWall system design is represented by multiple networked objects that are aware of each other's state at any given time. Figure 2 shows a system design with two nodes on each environment but the network can be expanded to hold multiple objects. These wireless objects are called buddies and each represent one remotely located friend. Buddies can be placed in a wall-mounted panel (the BuddyWall) or scattered throughout the house (figure 3).

Figure 2: BuddyWall networked system design.

Figure 3: Buddies can be placed in the wall panel or scattered throughout the house. By twisting the triangular control in the BuddyWall the user can broadcast his/her availability.

Like Amebeats, BuddyWall's design started as a rectangular panel with cubes representing remote friends. Since users responded positively to the curved edges and organic design of Amebeats, the BuddyWall interface evolved to be a round panel with oval objects. Since this is an emotional device, buddies' design evolved beyond being only an oval object. The final BuddyWall design was inspired by the work of the designer Karim Rashid (Rashid, 2001) that is characterized by curved edges, organic shapes and candy colors. The buddy's minimal design relates also to the idea of anthropomorphism as a way of making an object more emotionally appealing. Since objects represent people, feet were added to the design so that users could relate to the object as being a remote friend. In addition, feet are functional elements in keeping

the objects in an upward position when not connected to the wall structure. The idea was to maintain the design as simple as possible, leaving the rest of the personalization up to the user who can choose to add faces, stickers, clothes, hair, and so on.

Findings from Amebeats informed that users prefer interacting with graspable objects. For this reason, a large squeezable area was chosen instead of a small button or switch. The object's design consists of two parts: the translucent front displays lighting patterns while the rubber back establishes communication after being poked. The fact that Amebeats was a wall-mounted structure and not a table interface made it more visible and easy to interact with. Similarly to Amebeats, BuddyWall consists of a wall-mounted panel but buddies can be also placed in other locations.

User interactions

The primary mode of interaction with the system is as follows: When the user approaches the BuddyWall all of his contacts are made aware of his/her presence through sound and pulsating light. Besides this passive presence detection done by the system, the user can actively broadcast his current state to the network by setting his/her availability to online, away or offline using the control in the BuddyWall interface (figure 4). Each buddy has a unique color that identifies it. Its brightness indicates whether this friend is online, away or offline (figure 5). At a glance, it is possible to know each buddy's availability just by looking at the wall.

Figure 4: The triangular control on the BuddyWall interface serves for the user to broadcast his/her availability to his/her buddy list.

Figure 5: A buddy's brightness indicates its availability.

If the user wants to communicate with a friend that is online, the act of poking the buddy object will transmit a sound and make the correspondent buddy on the remote environment flash. The remote friend accepts the invitation by poking the buddy and a voice connection is opened between both (figure 6). In the case of a buddy being away or offline, poking it will open a one-way connection for a user to leave a message. A blinking buddy indicates that a message has been received. Users can listen to messages at a later time by poking the object. The user might also want to appear invisible to specific friends. He/she can do so by tilting selected buddies by 90 degrees, which puts them “to sleep”. Those selected buddies would then have no awareness of the user's presence (figure 7).

Figure 6: Users communicate with each other through their respective buddies.

the act of putting mary to “sleep” makes her see my status as offline.

Figure 7: Tilting a buddy by 90 degrees makes it have no awareness of the user's presence.

Technology and prototype development

The BuddyWall proposed design (figure 8) comprises a bluetooth-enabled computer running a control program written in AppleScript that communicates with the well-established software Skype through its Application Programming Interface (API). This same program also communicates with the physical buddy by sending data through the serial port. This data is sent to the buddy via the XBee Shield (Yarza, 2007) and Arduino microcontroller (Banzi et al., 2005) connected to the computer. Arduino is an open-source electronics prototyping platform based on flexible, easy-to-use hardware and software. Arduino can sense the environment by receiving input from a variety of sensors and can affect its surroundings by controlling lights, motors, and other actuators.

Figure 8: The BuddyWall technology uses Skype's API to manage calls and users status.

The control program sends information wirelessly to the buddy objects through an Arduino microcontroller with XBee shield connected to the computer. Each buddy also has an Arduino with XBee shield. The XBee shield receives information sent by the control program on the computer and the Arduino interprets it using a basic communication protocol and activates the LEDs accordingly.

The BuddyWall prototype consisted of two buddies, each connected to a different computer as well as a “fake” BuddyWall that showed six illuminated buddies with different levels of brightness (figure 9). This physical representation of the BuddyWall was built in order to help users visualize the concept. The idea of this prototype was to simulate each buddy belonging to a different environment.

Figure 9: The BuddyWall working prototype.

Each buddy contained one Arduino microprocessor, two LEDs and one button (figure 10). The button was used to place or answer a call. Pressing the button is the equivalent of poking the rubber back of the buddy. The 2 LEDs were used to indicate the user’s status. Both LEDs ON meant that the user was online. One LED ON meant that the user was away or unavailable. Both LEDs were OFF when the user was offline.

Figure 10: The two working buddies.

Each computer was running Skype and the control program monitored the status of the user

logged in the other computer. Changes of status would be immediately reflected on the other buddy's LEDs. Pressing the button placed a call, which made the remote buddy flash. Pressing the button on the other buddy answered the call.

User testing

The BuddyWall prototype was tested in March 2008 with 18 users with backgrounds in the following areas: Agronomy, Art, Biology, Business Marketing, Chemistry, Computer Engineering, Design, Journalism, Literature, Nursing, Nutrition and Retail.

To gather baseline information, participants were asked about their impressions regarding current virtual social networking tools. In general what users appreciate the most is keeping in touch with friends, maintaining an emotional connection and hearing someone's voice. They enjoy services that are simple, convenient and non intrusive. The majority of users complained about having to have a computer in order to interact with friends. They feel that it is difficult to express emotions in text and that there is a lack of a more intimate connection.

The BuddyWall concept addresses the needs expressed by users with regards to the current social networking tools. The vast majority of users appreciated the fact that BuddyWall does not require a computer. They mentioned that this made the interaction easy, simple, practical, less demanding and less formal. The BuddyWall being a tangible interface with no visible computer makes it less intimidating to users and thus could reach a wider audience: from kids to elders. Users appreciated the physicality of this interface – an aspect that has been mostly lost in current digital systems. With this interface they can touch, feel and instantly see the system's status in an intuitive way. Users felt more emotionally connected to the objects and stated that the communication is more intimate, fun and playful than the traditional communication mediated by computers. They see the interface as a toy rather than a computer program. Users appreciated the fact that the interaction was intuitive and non intrusive. They can dedicate their whole attention or just let it fade into the background. Regarding the interface's appearance, users stated that it is simple, decorative and aesthetically pleasing.

Users were also asked about their dislikes and if they would change anything in the system in order to better suit their needs. They pointed out that buddies are currently identified only by color, which makes it difficult to remember who is who unless they personalize them with accessories. Using only color for identification also poses a problem to color-blind people. Some users disliked the fact that buddies represent a one-to-one connection whereas with their

cell phone they can contact multiple people. Other users also noted that buddies depend on Internet availability, which is currently not so ubiquitous as cell phone availability.

Discussion

This project was created in response to a need to broaden human-computer interaction to human-human interaction, which has the purpose of connecting humans through emotion rather than connecting humans with machines. Technology should serve as a facilitator to human relationships. It should bring more to people's lives than the improved performance of tasks: it should add richness and enjoyment. By adding beauty, fun and pleasure, this project aims at producing enjoyment in order to bring positive emotions, which are essential to people's curiosity and ability to learn.

Besides focusing on tangibility to bring forth the emotional aspect of interaction, BuddyWall focuses on social interaction, enabling people to feel connected independent of location or time zone. Speech has been chosen as one of the main interaction techniques of this project since it is such a powerful social vehicle. It enables communication of emotional state through its natural prosody — pauses, rhythm, pitch, inflections, hesitations, and repeats. Besides speech, some design metaphors are used to facilitate interaction: light and sound are used as indication of remote presence, poking is used as a way of awakening a buddy and tilting is used as a way of putting a buddy into sleep mode. More of these ideas would be useful in an attempt to simplify this tangible user interface. For instance, olfaction could be used as a way of indicating one's presence the same way a person can feel the smell of one that is close by. The sense of touch could be further explored in order to bring forth the emotional aspect of interaction: heat could serve as an indication that a remote buddy is being held and vibration could represent a "nudge" to draw one's attention. The use of different materials could also add great value to the sense of touch. In addition, different sounds could be used to express emotions: soothing sounds in contrast to exciting ones can serve as a means of communicating a remote friend's current state.

Conclusion and future work

In this paper I have presented a wireless system that provides aesthetically pleasing and emotionally engaging remote communication seamlessly integrated to the physical environment. The current prototype contains one communication object (buddy) in each environment and it aimed at testing and validating the proposed interaction techniques and technologies that are pertinent to the scope of this project. Future developments will expand the number of buddies in

the network and also allow for them to connect with other communication devices such as Instant Messaging (IM) Software and e-mail. In these cases, voice messages would be translated into text and sent via the Internet to the appropriate application. By broadening the connection to other communication devices, this project can also reach anyone with access to e-mail or IM software.

Since a buddy is a physical representation of a virtual friend, they could also hold more information than only that friend's availability and possibility to contact. A buddy, being an augmented object with new types of properties, can collect everything related to a friend: photos, e-mails, videos, address, birthday, etc. If a RFID tagged buddy is brought close to a computer, the computer opens up a digital representation of him (i.e., a folder) and inside this folder there could be a series of files. The user could pick a piece of video to send to this friend by simply dragging it into the folder.

Users might also want to create awareness without initiating a conversation. It is a way of establishing a non-verbal emotional connection, a way of saying "I'm thinking of you." In this case, a constant rubbing gesture would send a glowing light to the remotely located friend. By sending constant glows or doing it in a certain pace users can agree with each other upon private meanings to their interaction. It will be interesting to explore the development of interpersonal emotional languages by understanding how users can communicate emotions in a non-verbal fashion only through light and sound.

A buddy's location can be another interesting information to convey. Since buddies are mobile and can be removed from the wall panel, it will be interesting to inform a user that the other is bringing its buddy to the room with him/her. This can be seen as another way of non-verbally communicating emotion.

In the future, I would like to implement a variety of different physical interactions, such as gesture recognition and explore new digital contents for the buddies, such as LCD displays for video communication.

References

Ambient Devices (2001) "Ambient Orb."

<http://www.ambientdevices.com/cat/orb/orborder.html>. Retrieved April 21, 2008.

Banzi et al. (2005) "Arduino Diecimila Microprocessor."

<http://www.arduino.cc/en/Main/ArduinoBoardDiecimila>. Retrieved April 21, 2008.

Chang et al. (2002) "ComTouch: Design of a Vibroactile Communication Device." Proceedings of DIS2002.

Chang et al. (2001) "LumiTouch: An Emotional Communication Device." CHI2001 Extended Abstracts.

Chen et al. (2006) "ComSlipper: An Expressive Design to Support Awareness and Availability." CHI2006 Extended Abstracts.

Deschamps-Sonsino, A. (2007) "Good Night Lamp." <http://www.goodnightlamp.com/>. Retrieved April 21, 2008.

Ishii, H. and Ullmer, B. (1997). "Tangible Bits: Towards Seamless Interfaces between People, Bits, and Atoms." CHI 1997, ACM Press, pp.234-241.

Haladjian, R. and Mével, O. (2006) "Nabaztag: the Wi-Fi enabled ambient bunny." <http://www.nabaztag.com/>. Retrieved April 21, 2008.

Norman, D. (2004) "Emotional design: why we love (or hate) everyday things."

Quintanilha, M. (2006) "Amebeats: Music production through haptic interface." <http://interactionthesis.wordpress.com/2007/02/09/amebeats/>. Retrieved April 21, 2008.

Rashid, K. (2001) "Karim Rashid: I Want to Change the World."

Weiser, M. (1991) "The Computer for the 21st Century." Scientific American, 265 (3), pp. 94-104.

Weiser, M. and Brown, J.S., (1995) "Designing Calm Technology." <http://www.ubiq.com/hypertext/weiser/calmtech/calmtech.htm>. Retrieved April 21, 2008.

Yarza, M. (2007) "XBee Shield." <http://www.arduino.cc/playground/Shields/Xbee01>. Retrieved April 21, 2008.